

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

BIOINDICATION OF WATERS OF THE NOVOSIBIRSK RESERVOIR BY CENTRIC DIATOMS

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Abstract

The article gives an assessment of the water quality of the parts of the Novosibirsk reservoir, which is the main source of drinking water for the population of the city of Novosibirsk, according to saprobity indicators of centric diatoms and provides data on their species composition for 2016–2017. In total, 12 species were identified in the plankton of the reservoir: *Stephanodiscus hantzschii*, *S. makarova*, *S. minutulus*, *S. neoastrea*, *Cyclostephanos dubius*, *C. invisitatus*, *Cyclotella atomus*, *C. meneghiniana*, *Discostella pseudostelligera*, *Aulacoseira ambigua*, *A. granulata*, *A. subarctica*, related to the following genera: *Aulacoseira* – 3, *Cyclostephanos* – 2, *Cyclotella* – 2, *Discostella* – 1, *Stephanodiscus* – 4. Of the 11 saprobity indicator species, broadly tolerant species (α - β) and dirty water species (β - α , α - β) were noted, which are found in different parts of the reservoir: upper, middle and lower, and in Berdsky Bay. In 2016–2017 according to the assessment of water in terms of saprobity of centric diatoms, it corresponded to the category of “satisfactory purity” in the upper part of the reservoir and in Berdsky Bay, and was “polluted” in its lower part. The middle part was “polluted” in 2016, and “satisfactory purity” in 2017.

Keywords: centric diatoms, phytoplankton, water quality, saprobity indicators, Novosibirsk reservoir.

Introduction.

To assess the water quality of water bodies, the bioindication method is widely used, where the indicator is phytoplankton. It is the first to respond to changes in aquatic ecosystems. One of the bioindicators reflecting anthropogenic pollution of water bodies are diatoms, including centric algae (2, 5).

The Novosibirsk reservoir is the main source of drinking water supply for the population of Novosibirsk. Therefore the quality of its waters must comply with sanitary and hygienic standards (8).

Saprobity is determined by the sensitivity of aquatic organisms to different contents of organic substances, being one of the indicators of water quality. In this case, lists of indicator species are used, where they are divided into zones that differ in different concentrations of organic substances in water (10, 11).

The purpose of this work is to assess the water quality of the parts of the Novosibirsk Reservoir according to the indicators of saprobity of centric diatoms found in phytoplankton based on their occurrence in a certain zone of the reservoir.

Materials and methods.

The article was written based on the processing of images of diatom valves obtained at the Institute of Water and Environmental Problems of the Siberian Branch

of the Russian Academy of Sciences (Barnaul) using a Hitachi S 3400N scanning electron microscope (SEM) during the examination of 12 quantitative samples of phytoplankton.

Their selection was carried out in August 2016 and 2017 from 7 hydrobiological alignments characterizing all parts of the water area of the Novosibirsk Reservoir: upper (Kamen-on-Obi, Maletino), middle (Chingis), lower (Bystrovka, Upper pool) and Berdsky Bay (Rechkunovka and Agroles) (Fig. 1) (8).

Phytoplankton samples from each of the sites were integrated before burning, combining different sampling horizons: the surface, the bottom, and different depths of the photic layer: 0.5S, 1S, 2S (S – is water transparency over the Secchi disk). Diatom valves were freed from chloroplasts and organic matter by cold burning (1). Identification of diatoms was carried out using the determinant (9).

The taxonomic list of centric diatoms is compiled taking into account modern ideas about the taxonomy of algae based on the database of the open Internet resource Algaebase (<http://www.algaebase.org>) (12). The indicators of saprobity of indicator species were taken from the works (2, 3).

Figure 1. Map-scheme of the location of hydrobiological alignments of the Novosibirsk reservoir: 1 – Kamen-on-Obi; 2 – Drevnyanka; 3 – Maletino; 4 – Spirino - Genghis; 5 – Ordynskoe – Nizhnyaya Kamenka; 6 – Borovoye – Bystrovka; 7 – Leninskoe – Sosnovka, 8 – Berdsky Bay, Agrol's; 9 – Berdsky Bay, Rechkunovka; 10 – Upper reaches of the dam of the Novosibirsk hydroelectric power station.

Results.

In 2016–2017 12 centric diatoms belonging to the following genera were found in samples of summer phytoplankton from the Novosibirsk Reservoir: *Aulacoseira* – 3, *Cyclostephanos* – 2, *Cyclotella* – 2, *Discostella* – 1, *Stephanodiscus* – 4. The following species have been identified among them: *Stephanodiscus hantzschii* Grunow, *S. makarova* Genkal, *S. minutulus* (Kützing) Cleve et Möller, *S. neoastraea* Håkansson et Hickel, *Cyclostephanos dubius* (Fricke) Round, *C. invisitatus* (Hohn et Hellermann) E.C. Theriot, Stoermer et Håkansson, *Cyclotella atomus* Hustedt, *C. meneghiniana* Kützing, *Discostella pseudostelligera*

(Hustedt) Houk et Klee, *Aulacoseira ambigua* (Grunow) Simonsen, *A. granulata* (Ehrenberg) Simonsen, *A. subarctica* (O. Müller) E.Y. Haworth (6, 7).

Analyzing the saprobity indices of centric diatoms and their occurrence in different parts of the Novosibirsk Reservoir, it is possible to assess the quality of its waters.

In 2016 in the upper part of the reservoir and in the Berdsky Bay, among the indicator species, broadly tolerant species (o-β) that can live in both clean and polluted waters predominate. In other parts of the reservoir, their number coincides with the species living in polluted waters (β-α, α-β) (Table 1).

Table 1 Saprobity indicators and the occurrence of centric algae in the plankton of the Novosibirsk reservoir in 2016

Species	Saprobity indicators	Upper part	Middle part	Lower part	Berdsky Bay
<i>Stephanodiscus hantzschii</i>	α-β	+	+	+	+
<i>S. minutulus</i>	o-β	+	–	+	+
<i>S. neoastraea</i>	o-β	+	+	+	+
<i>Cyclostephanos dubius</i>	o-β	+	+	+	+
<i>C. invisitatus</i>	o-β	+	–	+	+
<i>C. atomus</i>	o-β	–	+	–	–
<i>C. meneghiniana</i>	o-β	+	+	–	+
<i>Discostella pseudostelligera</i>	o-β	–	–	–	+
<i>Aulacoseira ambigua</i>	α-β	–	+	+	+
<i>A. granulata</i>	β-α	+	+	+	+
<i>A. subarctica</i>	α-β	+	+	+	+

Note: saprobity indicators: o-β – oligo-betamezosaprobnyaya; β-α – beta-alpha-mesosaprobnyaya; α-β – alpha-beta-mesosaprobnyaya zone.

In 2016 water quality indicators for saprobity indicators of centric diatoms were “satisfactory purity” in the upper part of the reservoir and in the Berdsky Bay and “polluted” in the middle and lower parts.

In 2017 in the upper and middle zones of the reservoir and in the Berd Bay, broadly tolerant species (o-β) are also in the lead, the number of which in its lower part coincides with the species living in polluted waters (β-α, α-β) (Table 2).

Table 2 Saprobity indicators and the occurrence of centric algae in the plankton of the Novosibirsk reservoir in 2017

Species	Saprobity indicators	Upper part	Middle part	Lower part	Berdsky Bay
<i>Stephanodiscus hantzschii</i>	α - β	+	+	+	+
<i>S. minutulus</i>	α - β	+	+	+	+
<i>S. neoastraea</i>	α - β	–	+	+	+
<i>Cyclostephanos dubius</i>	α - β	+	+	+	+
<i>C. invisitatus</i>	α - β	+	–	–	+
<i>C. meneghiniana</i>	α - β	+	+	+	+
<i>Aulacoseira ambigua</i>	α - β	–	–	+	+
<i>A. granulata</i>	β - α	+	+	+	+
<i>A. subarctica</i>	α - β	+	–	+	+

In 2017 water quality indicators for saprobity indicators of centric diatoms were “satisfactory cleanliness” in the upper, middle parts and in the Byrd Bay and “polluted” in its lower part.

This assessment of water quality for saprobity indicators does not correspond to the water quality determined for these parts of the reservoir by phytoplankton biomass (7) according to the integrated ecological classification of waters (4), which is due to incomplete accounting of saprobity indicators of all species living in these areas of the reservoir.

Conclusion.

In the Novosibirsk reservoir in 2016–2017 12 species of centric diatoms belonging to genera were found: *Aulacoseira* – 3, *Cyclostephanos* – 2, *Cyclotella* – 2, *Discostella* – 1, *Stephanodiscus* – 4.

Of the 11 saprobity indicator species broadly tolerant species (α - β) and dirty water species (β - α , α - β).

In 2016–2017 according to the assessment of water in terms of saprobity of centric diatoms, it corresponded to the category of “satisfactory purity” in the upper part of the reservoir and in Berdsky Bay, and was “polluted” in its lower part. The middle part was “polluted” in 2016 and “satisfactory purity” in 2017.

Findings.

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References:

- Ballonov I. M. Preparation of algae for electron microscopy // Methods of studying biogeocenoses of inland waters. – Moscow: The Science, 1975 – P. 87–90.
- Barinova, S. S. Algae-indicators in assessing the quality of the environment / S. S. Barinova, L. A. Medvedeva, O. V. Anisimova. - Moscow: Research Institute for Environmental Protection, 2000. – 150 p.
- Barinova, S. S. Biodiversity of algae-indicators of the environment / S. S. Barinova, L. A. Medvedeva, O. V. Anisimova. – Tel Aviv: Pilies Studio, 2006. – 498 p.
- Complex ecological classification of the quality of land surface waters / O. P. Oksiyuk [et al.] // Hydrobiological journal. – 1993. – V. 4. – P. 62–76.
- Mirnenko E. I. Trends in the study of algae - indicators of the marine environment / E. I. Mirnenko, N. S. Zakharenkova / Problems of ecology and protection of the technogenic region. – 2016. – V. 3–4. – P. 13–22.
- Mikhailov V. V. Centric diatoms in the plankton of the Novosibirsk Reservoir / V. V. Mikhailov // Ecological Readings – 2018: International scientific and practical conference dedicated to the 100-th anniversary of the formation of the Omsk State Agrarian University P.A. Stolypin (Omsk, June 04–06, 2018). - Omsk, 2018. – P. 204–207.
- Mikhailov V. V. Evaluation of the current ecological state of the Novosibirsk reservoir in terms of phytoplankton development: dis. Cand. Biol. Sciences: 06.06.01 / Mikhailov Vyacheslav Vladimirovich. – Tyumen, 2020. – 197 p.
- Long-term dynamics of the water-ecological regime of the Novosibirsk reservoir / V. M. Savkin [et al.]. – Novosibirsk: Publishing House of the Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 2014. – 393 p.
- Key to diatoms of Russia / M. S. Kulikovskii [et al.]. – Yaroslavl: Filigree, 2016. – 803 p.
- Sladечek V. General biological scheme of water quality / V. Sladечek // Sanitary and technical hydrobiology. - Moscow, 1967. - P. 26-31.
- Shitikov, V. K. Quantitative hydroecology: methods of system identification / V. K. Shitikov, G. S. Rozenberg, T. D. Zinchenko. - Tolyatti: IEVB RAS, 2003. - 463 p.
- Guiry, M. D. AlgaeBase. World-wide electronic publication [Electronic resource] / M. D. Guiry, G. M. Guiry. – National University of Ireland, Galway. – Access mode: <http://www.algaebase.org>. – (Accessed: 02.08.2021).